

FLORIDA STAKEHOLDER SEAFLOOR MAPPING PRIORITIZATION FOR 20-200m WATER DEPTHS

Florida Coastal Mapping Program, February 2025

Authors:

K.L. Erickson¹, C. Hapke², C. Yung³, N.A. Raineault¹, and R. Baumstark⁴

¹Florida Institute of Oceanography, Saint Petersburg, FL

²University of South Florida, College of Marine Science, Saint Petersburg, FL

³NOAA, Office of Coast Survey, Integrated Ocean and Coastal Mapping, Silver Spring, MD

⁴Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission, Fish and Wildlife Research Institute, Saint Petersburg, FL

Key words: Bathymetry, Florida seafloor mapping, Prioritization, Gap Analysis

Acknowledgements

This effort would not have been possible without the assistance of many National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Florida Institute of Oceanography, and Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission staff who contributed substantially.

For more information on this project, please visit:

The FCMaP 2023 prioritization webpage:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/0dcbae5a78464845be2eaf68e7e588fa>

The 2024 gap analysis webpage: <https://florida-coastal-mapping-program-fio-maps.hub.arcgis.com/pages/gap-analysis>

The FCMaP Hub: <https://florida-coastal-mapping-program-fio-maps.hub.arcgis.com/>

For more information on the State of Florida’s Seafloor Mapping Initiative (FSMI), please visit:

<https://www.floridagio.gov/pages/fsmi>

INTRODUCTION

Importance

Large-scale high-resolution coastal seafloor mapping is a daunting task but essential for the future of Florida's unique ecosystems and economic stability (Keenan et al., 2022). The topography of land dictates the weather and climate not only on a continental scale but smaller regional areas as well (Champagnac et.al., 2012). The marine environment, much like land, has mountains, rivers, unique ecosystems, shifting tectonic plates, erosion and sediment accretion that affect our oceans and in turn our coastline. Detailed bathymetry of the seafloor is just as essential to our everyday lives as detailed mapping of our geological landmasses.

Seafloor mapping initiatives, nationally and internationally, have gained leverage in recent years largely in part due to technological advances and to the amount of information seafloor mapping data can help produce, particularly with regards to current and future climate change risks and hazards. Seafloor mapping data analysis allows for science-based decisions surrounding navigational safety, infrastructure planning, red tide events, restoration planning, ecotourism, and the blue economy. Seafloor mapping data has numerous applications ranging from use by local government planning departments to state and federal protection and management of marine and coastal habitats. Seafloor mapping data provides an understanding of how the seafloor affects our oceans which can be used to improve use and management for fisheries, aquaculture, renewable energy, tourism, shipping, and marine biotechnology (Florida Alliance: <https://www.floridaoceanalliance.org/blue-economy>). This underscores the importance of seafloor mapping for Florida and other coastal areas as well.

Mapping Coordination Needs

It's important to efficiently coordinate Florida's seafloor mapping and data needs. Being coordinated, effective and efficient, allows for the best utilization of time and equipment to ensure that the motto "map once, use many times" is applicable and justifies the immense cost of data collection. To accomplish efficient and effective mapping efforts, strategic partnerships are required, as well as coordinated efforts to support multi-organizational objectives and goals (i.e., scientists, industry, tribal organizations, as well as local, State and Federal governments).

A community approach to facilitate the discovery and data collection of common mapping interests not only involves networking and collaboration but also provides a mechanism for interested organizations to share mapping interests amongst multiple groups. The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science (NCCOS) developed a geospatial perspective of mapping priorities and online tool to identify mapping priorities across organizations (Kendall et al., 2015). This spatial mechanism allows

each group to specify their priority needs while utilizing a spatial framework that provides an overlay of each interested organization's priority response. Overlapping interested organization responses helps identify common priority areas across organizations, which will help educate and guide future funded mapping efforts.

The Florida Coastal Mapping Program (FCMaP) conducted a formal statewide seafloor mapping prioritization of Florida's coastal waters (0–200 m) in 2019 (Hapke et. al., 2022). This prioritization was Florida-centric with an overarching goal to develop an approach specific to coastal Florida yet be consistent with other prioritization efforts. The approach helped provide the best allocation of resources to leverage mapping efforts and build a comprehensive high-resolution (minimum mapping requirement of point spacing that supports a 1m DEM in the 0-10m, 3m in 10-20, and 10m DEM in deeper water), bathymetric dataset focused on coastal Florida. The overarching message from the 2019 prioritization was that the vast majority of mapping needs were focused in 20 m or less depth range (Hapke et. al., 2022). The approach used in the 2019 study proved to be effective and replicable (Hapke et al., 2022) and was used to help guide the Florida Seafloor Mapping Initiative (FSMI; <https://www.floridagov.gov/pages/fsmi>); a State-administered program to map Florida's coastal seafloor.

During the FCMaP 2022 Annual Summit participants were asked to provide feedback on 0-200 m depths prioritization maps that were developed in 2019; this time with a focus on the 20-200 m depths to assess whether the 2019 prioritization was still relevant. The participant feedback triggered the effort to conduct the 2023 prioritization, focused specifically on the 20-200 m water depth, discussed here.

The 2019 prioritization approach specifically used NOAA's spatial framework process and online tool (Costa et. al., 2019) for consistency and efficiency, and was determined to be the best approach for the 2023 prioritization. However, the 2023 prioritization approach was designed to be more cohesive within a national framework.

The objective of the 2023 prioritization and this paper is to identify priority locations at the 20 – 200 m water depths that are most beneficial to the interested and impacted organizations, which can help guide Florida's future seafloor mapping efforts.

The FCMaP goal is to have these prioritization results inform future data collections by agencies and private industry and specifically to assist with future FSMI deep-water data acquisition planning efforts.

METHODS

Participants

To engage science, industry, and government communities with interest in mapping data or products to participate in the FCMaP 2019 prioritization study, a series of five regional workshops were held across the state and in total represented 219 interested organizations (Hapke et. al., 2022). For the 2023 prioritization, an initial list of participants was created by compiling a list of individuals contacted to participate in the 2019 prioritization. This initial list was reviewed by the FCMaP Science and Technical Advisory Committee (STAC) to determine gaps in the represented stakeholders. An effort was then made to reach out to potentially interested and impacted entities to gain contact information within those underrepresented communities (i.e., recreational fishers, tribal organizations, State, and water management districts).

FCMaP held a virtual workshop in June 2023 to review the 2019 prioritization efforts, encourage broad participation from all organizations, provide instructions on how to assign a prioritization organizational point of contact (POC), and how the POC would use the online prioritization tool. The goal was to have one representative (POC) participate on behalf of their organization/department. Once the interested organizations established their POC, an account was created for each to access the online platform to participate in the prioritization.

Collection Grid

A 10x10 km grid covering Florida Shelf waters between 20-200m depth was derived from the larger USGS 3DEP grid (3D Elevation Program: <https://www.usgs.gov/3d-elevation-program>) (Figures 1 and 2.) This prioritization grid provides a spatial layer for participants to designate priority locations for mapping.

Figure 1. Collection grid (between 20-200m depth) overlaid with bathymetric contours.

Application / Online Tool

The prioritization application was designed using ESRI's Web AppBuilder and incorporated the Spatial Prioritization Widget, designed by the National Centers for Coastal and Ocean Science (NCCOS) for previous regional prioritization studies (Buja and Christensen, 2019). This prioritization application allows participants to identify their priorities and describe their mapping interests by selecting and attributing spatial locations from a prioritization grid.

The prioritization application and grid were modified slightly for the 2023 FCMaP prioritization (20-200m) study. In prior NCCOS and FCMaP prioritization studies, participants were asked to assign a numerical "coin" value to the locations of interest for their organization. Higher numbers of coins equated to a higher priority. In the 2023 prioritization study, participants were asked to assign a High (map within 1-2 years), Medium (map within 3-5 years), or Low (map within 6-10 years) value to each cell. The High, Medium, Low method allows the study results to be defined in terms of how soon mapping data are needed in a given location, with High priority corresponding to the most urgent need. Drop down Justification and Map Product

menu selections were also modified for the 2023 prioritization study. The prioritization application user interface is web based and does not require software installation (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Example of the Spatial Prioritization Widget used in the FCMaP 2: Deep-water (20-200 m) Prioritization Study.

Criteria

The Spatial Prioritization Widget included the following drop-down menus:

- Priority - location and priority/urgency of mapping priorities
- Primary Justification, Secondary Justification, and Tertiary Justification (why do you need this area mapped?)
- Primary Map Product, Secondary Map Product, and Tertiary Map Product (what data do you need from this area?)
- Horizontal Resolution (what spatial resolution is desired for your priority area?)

Priority

Participants used the drop-down menus to designate priority levels for each grid selection (Table 1). The priority method High/Medium/Low was chosen for a number of reasons. In prior studies, regional prioritization surveys generally used the coin method, which allowed for robust statistical analysis. However, the coin method may not be easily understood by the end users of the map results who did not themselves enter data in the study. The coin method also does not assign a strict timeline to mapping data needs. For these reasons, the 2023

prioritization study used the High/Medium/Low method to make the prioritization results more easily interpretable over 10 years.

Selection rules were defined to limit the number of cells that users could allocate to High, Medium, or Low selections. The rules were defined to force study participants to limit their high and medium priority locations to relatively few cells to make the highest mapping priorities more apparent when responses were combined.

The rules were as follows:

- Participants could only select up to 10% of total grid cells as High.
- Participants could only select up to 25% of total grid cells as Medium.
- Participants could only select up to 50% of total grid cells as Low.
- All un-prioritized cells were assigned the priority of None.

While participants had percentage limits for selection, they were not required to meet these limits. This ensured that participants only prioritized areas that were of interest to them and did not add extra priorities in order to meet submission requirements, ensuring true priority areas were captured.

Priority	
Criterion	Details
None	Mapping needed, but not within next 10 years
Low	Mapping need in 6-10 years (<50% of cells)
Medium	Mapping need in 3-5 years (<25% of cells)
High	Mapping Need in 1-2 years (<10% of cells)

Table 1. Criteria options for “Priority” allocations provided in the 2023 prioritization study Spatial Prioritization widget.

Justification

Within the application, respondents were able to provide up to three different justifications for each prioritized cell: primary, secondary, and tertiary to explain the purpose for the mapping priority (Table 2). This allowed participants to identify multiple rationales for their mapping needs. Only the primary justification selection was required. Primary, secondary, and tertiary justifications were all weighted equally in the study results.

Justification: Purpose for Mapping	
Criterion	Details
Benthic Exploration	Targeted benthic exploration for seafloor characterization
Water column exploration	Targeted water column exploration for water column characterization (e.g. upwelling, seeps, biological origin, biotoxins, harmful algae)
Commercial and recreational fishing	Fisheries management and regulation (e.g. commercial/recreational fishing locations, aquaculture siting, fisheries sampling stations, high bycatch areas, sport/charter fishing)
Cultural/historical resources	Shipwrecks, tribal use areas and other archaeological/cultural/historic resources
Energy	Energy permitting, siting, management, transmission (e.g. oil/natural gas platforms, deep water ports, wind turbine, tidal/hydropower, cables, pipelines, etc.)
Habitat/biota/natural area	Includes Essential Fish Habitat, Critical Habitat (for marine mammals and other protected species, spawning/nursery areas, feeding grounds, key benthic habitats, habitat mapping, coastal geomorphology and other ecologically significant areas
Coastal/Marine natural hazards	Detection, forecast and management of coastal and marine hazards, including weather/storm surge, flooding, tsunamis, earthquakes, geologic faults, harmful algae blooms, etc.
Infrastructure (non-energy)	Existing or potential infrastructure development, includes port facilities, bridges, telecommunication cables, roads, etc.
Protection/Management Areas	Marine protected area, sanctuaries, conservation areas, restoration sites, dynamic management areas for marine mammals and other protected species
Monitoring	Monitoring of specific study areas for scientific or other purposes (such as coral health monitoring, invasive species monitoring, etc.)
Modeling	Modeling of specific study areas for scientific or other purposes
Navigation safety	Safe navigation in U.S. waters, e.g. shipping lanes, ferry routes, harbors/approaches, port facilities and marinas; includes detection of hazards to navigation (rocks, wrecks, other obstructions)
Scientific research	General scientific research, not including monitoring of a specific area
Mineral resources	Critical and base mineral resources, aggregate resources for beach renourishment and/or heavy sands mineral resource, other non-energy mineral resources
Sediment transport	Sediment movement and management needs, managing beach erosion/renourishment or sediment buildups in channels and ports

Recreational activities (other than fishing)	Recreational activities (e.g. boating, ecotourism, swimming and diving)
Public health	Contaminants and hazards that could impact communities, subsistence cultures and food safety (e.g. seafood safety) such as contaminated sediments, marine biotoxins, chemicals around oil wells and pipelines, waste and dredge material dumping sites, etc.
Climate Change Analysis	Research and modeling focused on climate change related Sea Level Rise (SLR) and other projections for long term planning

Table 2. Criteria options for justification allocations provided in the 2023 prioritization (20-200m) prioritization application.

Map Product

Participants used the drop-down menus to designate up to three different map product needs for each prioritization location (Table 3). This allowed participants to identify multiple data products they may wish to acquire from the same priority area. Only the primary selection was required. Primary, secondary, and tertiary map products were all weighted equally in the results.

Map Product	
Criterion	Details
None	None
Elevation (bathymetry/topography)	Measurement of height/depth of seabed or coastal terrain. Collected using multibeam sonar, airborne LiDAR or other methods. Processed into bathy grids, Digital Elevation Models for a wide variety of downstream products
Backscatter intensity	Seabed imagery of reflected intensity (acoustic or optical) for location and distribution of different substrate types and habitat
Magnetometer surveys	For detection of magnetic anomalies, ferrous objects, man-made objects or evidence of human activity, cultural resources surveys, archaeological assessment, unexploded ordinance, wrecks, debris.
Photographs/videos/imagery (surface or underwater)	Imagery of seabed/benthos/water column. Includes video and still imagery in all spectral bands. May be collected with ROVs, AUVs, other camera platforms, satellites, etc.
Biological, chemical or physical samples	Samples collected from seafloor/subseafloor/water column using divers, AUVs, ROVs, cores, grabs, CTDs, rosettes, etc.

Substrate/Sub-bottom geologic characterization	Remote-sensing derived (i.e. seismic, chirp sub-bottom, multibeam sonar, sub-bottom profiling sonars, magnetic susceptibility, self-potential) seafloor type and characteristics (i.e. hardness/roughness/thickness/grain size/substrate type/mineralogy, etc.)
Water column mapping/characterization	Commonly collected with multibeam/split-beam sonar systems; used to identify bubbles, plankton layers, fish, harmful algae, biotoxins, seeps, etc.
Shoreline characterization/topographic maps	Delineation and characterization of shoreline/coastal topography/coastal infrastructure and features (port facilities, boat ramps, docks, pipe landfalls, etc.)
Habitat map/characterization	Identification/suitability of benthic environment and habitat distribution; derived from remote sensing, optical imaging, and physical sampling
Nautical map and chart products	Electronic Navigational Charts, other products for navigation
Human use statistics	Socioeconomic, demographic, and other statistics regarding human use of ocean areas
Wildlife population characterization	Includes marine mammal, bird, sea turtle surveys; stock assessments
Ocean use infrastructure site maps	Delineation and characterization of oil platforms, wells, pipelines, wastewater treatment plant outfalls, waste dredge material dump sites, shipping lanes, and aquaculture sites
Land use impacts on coastal zone	Location and metadata from wastewater treatment plant inputs and seepages, riverine runoff, stormwater runoff, and other impacts from manmade coastal zone inputs
Other mapping products not listed	

Table 3. Criteria options for “Map Products” allocations provided in the 2023 prioritization (20-200m) Spatial Prioritization widget.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In total, 22 POCs provided information on their organization’s priority mapping needs using the online tool (Table 4). The majority of respondents were Federal agencies (45.5%) with State government, local government and research or academic institution sectors, each resulting in 18% participation (Figure 3). The 2023 prioritization had increased State government representation compared to the 2019 prioritization. However, no recreational fishermen participated, and tribal representation was lacking as they chose not to participate at this time. Participation of government organizations is important to capture resource management

decision needs while input from research and academic institutions provides perspective on important science needs.

Responding Organizations	
1	Bay County Tourist Development Council
2	Bureau of Ocean Energy Management
3	Center for Ocean Mapping and Innovative Technology
4	City of Deerfield Beach
5	Department of Energy, Water Power Technologies Office
6	Environmental Protection Agency, Ocean Dumping Program
7	Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services
8	Florida Department of Environmental Protection, Beaches Program
9	Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission, Fish and Wildlife Research Institute
10	Florida Department of Environmental Protection, Florida Geological Survey
11	National Marine Fisheries Service, Fisheries and Regional Offices
12	National Park Service
13	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, Florida Navigation
14	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science
15	Pinellas County
16	Sarasota County Government
17	South Florida Water Management District
18	United States Coast Guard
19	United States Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service
20	United States Geological Survey
21	University of Florida, Center for Coastal Solutions
22	University of Florida, Institute of Food and Agricultural Sciences extension: Bay County Board of Commissioners

Table 4. Organizational participants in the FCMaP 2023 Prioritization.

Figure 3. Distribution of agencies and institutions that participated in the FCMaP prioritization.

The resulting map indicates the highest priority areas for the State of Florida with darker colors (reds and oranges) indicating a higher number of interested respondents (Figure 4). The highest priority areas (1-2 years) fall into the shallower 20-40 m water depth areas off of the Panhandle, Big Bend Region, Tampa Bay, and the Florida Keys up to West Palm Beach. The 20-40 m areas appear to be offshore extensions of the 2019 prioritization which were focused on the shallower water areas (0-20 m water depth). In areas like the Florida Keys, the 20-40 m water depths are home to mesophotic reefs that are not well mapped. The coastal area off of Miami ranked as a high priority, which could support the desire to obtain information on habitat loss and bottom type for resource management of the Biscayne Bay National Park Service (<https://floridadep.gov/rcp/aquatic-preserve/content/management-issues-biscayne-bay-aquatic-preserves>). Deeper areas (>40 m) ranked medium and low priority are off the Panhandle, Tampa Bay, and west of the Florida Keys. West of Cape Coral and south of the Panhandle, low priority was indicated around the 200 m depth, likely for sand resources. Most of the high and medium priority areas were selected in the nearshore areas of the prioritization grid and correspond to areas that are typically too deep for lidar penetration (the focus of the FSMI efforts) and require more labor-intensive methodologies to survey with acoustic systems.

Figure 4. Results of the statewide prioritization based on a ranking system of low (yellow), medium (orange), and high (red) temporal priority.

The results of the statewide summed prioritization for Florida, based on the number of respondents, show prioritization regardless of timeline (Figure 5). The summed prioritization is created by aggregating the ranked values (high=3, medium=2, and low=1) of each selected grid cell, essentially showing all priority areas without taking into consideration a prioritized timeline. The summed prioritization is not intended for planning data collection but rather indicates all areas where seafloor mapping within 20-200 m off the coast of Florida is desired. The summed priority map aligns with the high priority map (Figure 4) indicating that the shallower (20-40 m) area is of the most interest statewide. The summed prioritization map provides an overview of where respondents eventually want mapping data collected. Unlike the high priority map (Figure 4), the summed prioritization (Figure 5) shows the importance placed in the shallow and deep waters along Northeastern Florida as well as in deeper offshore waters of Western Florida.

Figure 5. Results of the statewide prioritization based on the number of respondents.

Mapping Products

Elevation is the highest priority mapping product with 31% of respondents indicating this category as the primary data type desired, followed by backscatter intensity and sub-bottom characterization, 27% and 22% respectively (Figure 6). The top three mapping products make up 80% of the data types prioritized in the study. It should be noted that acoustic survey systems collecting elevation data typically also collect backscatter, but backscatter systems (e.g. side-scan and synthetic aperture sonar) typically are not capable of collecting bathymetric elevation. Backscatter data and seafloor samples combined with bathymetric elevation (e.g. multibeam sonar) are useful in mapping seafloor type and inferring biological cover, which provides habitat data important to fisheries and resource management (Roff and Taylor, 2000).

Sub-bottom profiles provide subsurface stratigraphy and structure information that can be used for geological studies, identifying pathways for ocean gases and cultural artifacts.

Magnetometers measure changes in magnetic fields and provide data to characterize geological seafloor features and discover cultural heritage sites.

Figure 6. Frequency of selected mapping products for high priority mapping choice.

Elevation as a needed mapping product is widely distributed around the State. Backscatter was indicated as the second highest priority mapping product and almost mirrors that of elevation throughout the State waters (Figure 7a and 7b). Sub-bottom needs align with the high priority map along the shallow areas of the Panhandle Region and Eastern Coast of Florida. The top three mapping products, elevation (Figure 7a), backscatter (Figure 7b) and sub-bottom (Figure 7c) were all selected as important in the Panhandle region and in the shallow areas along Eastern Florida. The interest in backscatter and sub-bottom could support the need for habitat mapping and sediment sources for beach renourishment (<https://florida-coastal-mapping-program-fio-maps.hub.arcgis.com/pages/fcmap-news-meetings-and-reports>). The fourth ranked mapping product, chemical and physical sampling, are indicated as a priority, albeit relatively low, along the shallow Panhandle, Big Bend and along the Western coast of Florida.

Figure 7. Geospatial distribution of the top three categories of mapping products as indicated by prioritization tool respondents: a) elevation; b) backscatter intensity; c) substrate, sub bottom.

Mapping Justification

The mapping justification response provides insight on the intended uses of and important applications for the seafloor mapping data. Scientific research is the most desired mapping data justification at 36%, followed by habitat/biota/natural area at 18% and modeling at 16% (Figure 8). The top three mapping justifications make up 70% of the survey responses. The scientific research justification likely indicates a general need for better data in order to increase the scientific understanding of areas where mapping was prioritized. The modeling justification category provides insight on where seafloor mapping data is an important dataset needed to inform modeling efforts such as ocean circulation, sediment transport, and ecosystem and fishery assessments.

Figure 8. Frequency of selected mapping products for high priority mapping choice.

Based on the distribution of priorities for scientific research, it appears the entire Florida seafloor in the 20-200 m depth zones is considered important (Figure 9a) with the highest interest off Miami-Dade. The percentage of respondents that ranked scientific research as high priority (36%) is possibly due to high academic and federal government participation in the 2023 prioritization. Surprisingly, climate change analysis was not selected by any respondents. Climate change analysis is a broad topic however, and the top categories selected can inform many climate changes studies. Therefore, the respondents may instead have selected a more general justification. The results of the mapping justification show that there are 3 main

reasons respondents want high priority areas mapped as they fall within the 20-40m depth (Figure 9a) and align with both the high priority map (Figure 4) and the summed prioritization map (Figure 5).

Based on the distribution of priorities, habitat, biota, and natural areas are important throughout coastal Florida leaving only a few gaps in the deeper water off Western Florida (Figure 9b). The priority areas throughout the Florida Keys and Southeast Florida are especially understandable as it includes the Florida Coral Reef Tract which could support an interest in mapping coral reef and hardbottom habitat (<https://florida-coastal-mapping-program-fio-maps.hub.arcgis.com/pages/fcmap-news-meetings-and-reports>). While the deeper water off Western Florida is not an immediate priority for habitat, biota, and natural areas, mapping is of importance as indicated in the summed priority map (Figure 5).

Data for modeling (Figure 9c) is a high priority and widely distributed throughout Florida waters except for the mid-water depth of Western Florida. The greatest interest in modeling was in the coastal and shallow areas of Eastern Florida and down through the Florida Keys. These areas are likely high priority due to the vulnerability and fragile ecosystems of the Florida Keys and the large population at risk of flooding and storms in the coastal areas.

Figure 9. Geospatial distribution of the top three categories of justifications as indicated by prioritization tool respondents: a) scientific research; b) habitat, biota, natural area; and modeling; c) modeling.

Based on the 2017 gap analysis (Hapke et al., 2019), the Big Bend Region was a sparsely mapped region that was not a high priority area in the 2019 prioritization (Table 5). There are fragile natural resources in this area, which include the Big Bend Seagrass aquatic preserve (<https://floridadep.gov/rcp/aquatic-preserve/locations/big-bend-seagrasses-aquatic-preserve>) and the recently designated (2020) Nature Coast Aquatic Preserve (<https://floridadep.gov/NatureCoastAP>). Result of the 2023 prioritization indicate higher priority interest in protection/resource management in the Keys however, the results did not indicate that the Big Bend area was a high priority. Currently much of the Big Bend shallow water areas (0-20 m) have been mapped or soon will be as part of the Florida Seafloor Mapping Initiative (FSMI). Improved mapping data in the Big Bend region will provide information to better understand this historically low priority area and potentially shed more light on critical resources in the area. Potentially resulting in higher priority needs for the Big Bend region in the future and underscoring the importance of re-examining prioritization results periodically (<https://florida-coastal-mapping-program-fio-maps.hub.arcgis.com/pages/fcmap-news-meetings-and-reports>).

2024 Gap Analysis Comparison to Summed Priority Map

The results of the 2024 gap analysis (i.e., a method to determine areas of seafloor that are lacking high-resolution bathymetric data) indicate a substantial increase in the percentage of Florida's nearshore coastal seafloor (0-20 m) mapped since 2017 (Table 5). In 2017 an average of only 27% of the coastal nearshore seafloor had been mapped using high-resolution technologies (Hapke et. al., 2022). Currently, 99.4% of the coastal nearshore seafloor has been or is being mapped using modern high-resolution technologies (Table 5). The FSMI was partly guided by the Florida mapping community 2019 prioritization results. Most significant is the poorly mapped Big Bend region, which was previously only 3% mapped, is now at 100% mapping coverage. This substantial increase in mapping coverage of the 0-20 m in the Big Bend region is due to the efforts of the FSMI. The additional mapping data will be useful for resource management and the region could become a higher priority in future prioritization studies as the mapping data provides more information.

There has also been progress in mapping coverage offshore (20-200 m), with the West Florida Peninsula increasing from 8% to 16%, Southeast Florida rising from 20% to 64% and Northeast Florida increasing from 4% to 34%. However, while there has been a lot of progress, high-resolution data is still lacking in the 20-200 m especially along the West Florida Self and outer portion of Northeastern Florida.

2017 Percentage of Mapped Area by Region			2024 Percentage of Mapped Area by Region		
Regions	Nearshore (0-20m)	Offshore (20-200m)	Regions	Nearshore (0-20m)	Offshore (20-200m)
Panhandle	44%	43%	Panhandle	100%	56%
Big Bend	3%	23%	Big Bend	100%	35%
West FL Peninsula	28%	8%	West FL Peninsula	100%	16%
Florida Keys	27%	19%	Florida Keys	99%	42%
Southeast FL	83%	20%	Southeast FL	99%	64%
Northeast	60%	4%	Northeast	98%	34%
All Regions	27.00%	16%	All Regions	99.40%	34%

Table 5. Gap analysis comparison of percentage of mapped area by region in 2017 and 2024. The 2024 gap analysis results assume completion of the planned nearshore data collection of the Florida Seafloor Mapping Initiative (<https://www.floridagio.gov/pages/fsmi>).

The 2024 gap analysis map overlaid onto the summed priority map (Figure 5) illustrates where there are priority areas within areas lacking high-resolution data (gap areas; Figure 10). A large portion of the 2023 high priority areas identified in the 20–40 m depth range are data gaps along Eastern and Western Florida. This information is important given the FSMI began deep-water data acquisition in 2024. The deeper 40-200 m areas off eastern and western Florida are a high mapping priority, which were unmapped as of 2023. The Florida Keys out to the Dry Tortugas is a high priority area according to the 2023 prioritization but has high-resolution mapping coverage (Figure 5). These are areas that likely need to be considered for more frequent mapping due to being an area of dynamic seafloor and coral reef change caused by storms, coral disease, and climate change impacts including coral bleaching (<https://floridadep.gov/rcp/coral/content/stony-coral-tissue-loss-disease-response>).

Figure 10. The 2024 gap analysis overlaid onto the 2023 prioritization. Green areas have been mapped. The 2024 gap analysis results assume completion of the planned nearshore data collection of the Florida Seafloor Mapping Initiative (<https://www.floridagio.gov/pages/fsmi>).

Conclusions

The importance of seafloor mapping is recognized worldwide for risk assessments, resource conservation, marine economy and navigational safety. However, seafloor mapping is expensive, which underscores the importance of identifying mapping priorities that are most beneficial to interested organizations. By determining the spatial results of overlapping stakeholder data needs, mapping priorities can be used to make data collection more efficient by leveraging resources and coordinating and surveying high priority locations throughout coastal Florida. The FCMaP prioritization is the fourth regional study, as Alaska (<https://aocs.org/wp-content/uploads/2019-AK-Coastal-Mapping-Prioritization-Survey-final-web.pdf>), EXPRESS (<https://www.usgs.gov/centers/pcmssc/science/express-expanding-pacific->

[research-and-exploration-submerged-systems](#)) and the Great Lakes (<https://www.usgs.gov/publications/great-lakes-spatial-priorities-study>) have also conducted prioritizations in collaboration with NOAA. While NOAA has been conducting several nationwide prioritizations, the regional level prioritizations provide clarity and help with regional partnerships.

The undertaking of seafloor mapping stakeholder prioritizations at the statewide level are not a trivial effort but were recognized by the FCMaP Science and Technical Advisory Council as critical to informing any mapping efforts (Hapke et al., 2022), and the 2017 gap analysis (Hapke et al., 2019) quickly led to some larger data collection efforts by NOAA. Eventually, the messaging regarding the paucity of data and how important seafloor data is for the Blue Economy of Florida persuaded the Florida Legislature, in 2022, to budget \$100 million for seafloor mapping. This was realized by the creation of the FSMI (see link below) administered by the Florida Department of Environmental Protection. As of early 2025, topobathymetric lidar has been collected for the entire state in the 0-20 m water depth (unless lidar could not resolve to seafloor due to lack of water clarity). The decision to focus on the 0-20m depth zone in the initial FSMI phases was influenced by the FCMaP original prioritization. In addition, the later phases of the FSMI mapping that require sonar technologies and are largely focused in the 20-40 m water depth, were also informed by the FCMaP deeper water prioritization (discussed in this report). This demonstrates the inherent value of conducting regional prioritizations and the true success FCMaP and FSMI were able to achieve.

The objective of the 2023 FCMaP prioritization was to identify the priority mapping locations in the 20 – 200 m water depth most beneficial to the participating organizations. The 2023 prioritization results indicate the strongest need for high resolution seafloor data in the 20–40 m depth range which also fall within areas of data gaps, specifically along eastern and western Florida. Deeper water areas (40-200 m), overall indicate a higher priority as well, especially in the northeast, just not as urgently (Figure 4).

The mapping products results show the need for multibeam sonar data, backscatter data and physical seafloor samples for indicating seafloor type and biological cover, which provides habitat data for fisheries and resource management. This is of great importance to recreational fisheries in Florida which is a major economic driver (FL Alliance, <https://www.floridaoceanalliance.org/blue-economy>). The mapping justification results indicate the collection of high-resolution priority data that will provide a better scientific understanding of the seafloor and allow for increased data for understanding ocean circulation, sediment transport, and ecosystem and fishery assessments.

The 2023 priority mapping products and justifications provide a better understanding of the FCMaP communities' needs for deep-water (20-200 m) seafloor data.

The FCMaP goal is to have these prioritization results inform future data collections by agencies and private industry and specifically to assist with future FSMI deep-water data acquisition planning efforts.

REFERENCES

- Alaska Coastal Mapping Prioritization Survey: <https://aoos.org/wp-content/uploads/2019-AK-Coastal-Mapping-Prioritization-Survey-final-web.pdf>
- Buja, K. and J. Christensen. 2019. Spatial Prioritization Widget: A Tool to Identify Mapping Priorities. Available online: <https://coastalscience.noaa.gov/project/spatial-prioritization-widget/> (Accessed 5 April, 2021).
- Biscayne Bay Aquatic Preserves Management Issues, <https://floridadep.gov/rcp/aquatic-preserve/content/management-issues-biscayne-bay-aquatic-preserves>
- Champagnac, J.D., P. Molnar, C. Sue, and F. Herman. 2012. Tectonics, climate, and mountain topography, *J. Geophysical Research*, 117, (B02403). [doi:10.1029/2011JB008348](https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JB008348)
- Costa, B., K. Buja, M. Kendall, B. Williams, J. Kraus. 2019. Prioritizing Areas for Future Seafloor Mapping, Research, and Exploration Offshore of California, Oregon, and Washington. NOAA Technical Memorandum NOS NCCOS 264. Silver Spring, MD. 80 p. [doi:10.25923/wa5c-vn25](https://doi.org/10.25923/wa5c-vn25)
- Expanding Pacific Research and Exploration of Submerged Systems (EXPRESS), (<https://www.usgs.gov/centers/pcm/science/express-expanding-pacific-research-and-exploration-submerged-systems>)
- Florida Coastal Mapping Program 2024 Annual Summit Report, <https://florida-coastal-mapping-program-fio-maps.hub.arcgis.com/pages/fcmap-news-meetings-and-reports>
- Florida Department of Environmental Protection <https://floridadep.gov/rcp/coral/content/stony-coral-tissue-loss-disease-response>
- Florida Ocean Alliance; <https://www.floridaoceanalliance.org/articles-publications/>; last accessed 10/26/2020
- Florida Ocean Alliance <https://www.floridaoceanalliance.org/blue-economy>
- Florida Seafloor Mapping Initiative (FSMI); <https://www.floridagio.gov/pages/fsmi>
- Great Lakes, <https://www.usgs.gov/publications/great-lakes-spatial-priorities-study>
- Hapke, C.J., P.A. Kramer, E.H. Fetherston-Resch, R.D. Baumstark, R. Druyor, X. Fredericks, and E. Fitos. 2019. Florida Coastal Mapping Program—Overview and 2018 Workshop Report. *Open-File Report*, (2019-1017).

Hapke, C., R. Baumstark, R. Druyor, X. Fredericks, P. Kramer, K. Jackson, and L. McEachon. 2022. Establishing seafloor mapping priorities for coastal states. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 216, (105942).

Keenan, S. F., T. Switzer, A Knapp, E. J. Weather, and J Davis. 2022. Spatial dynamics of the quantity and diversity of natural and artificial hard bottom habitats in the eastern Gulf of Mexico. *Continental Shelf Research*, 233, (104633). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2021.104633>

Kendall, M.S., K. Buja, C. Menza, and T. Battista. 2018. Where, What, When, and Why is bottom mapping needed? An on-line application to set priorities using expert opinion. *Geosciences*: 8, (26).

Reed, J.K., S. Farrington, M.C. Diaz, S.A. Pomponi, M.D. Hanisak, J. D. Voss. 2021. Characterization of the Mesophotic Coral Reefs in the Florida Keys National Marine Sanctuary. NOAA CIOERT Report, Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institution Technical Report Number 198, 222 p. <http://www.cioert.org/expeditions/mesophotic-reef-ecosystems>

Roff, J.C. and M.E., Taylor. (2000) National Frameworks for Marine Conservation—A Hierarchical Geophysical Approach. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems*, 10, 209-223 pp. [Doi:10.1002/1099-0755](https://doi.org/10.1002/1099-0755)

USGS 3D Elevation Program; <https://www.usgs.gov/3d-elevation-program>